

Source data index for:

Single molecule studies reveal branched pathways for activator-dependent assembly of RNA polymerase II pre-initiation complexes

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Source data for the single-molecule experiments is provided as “intervals” files that can be read and manipulated by the Matlab program “Imscroll”, which is publicly available:

https://github.com/gelles-brandeis/CoSMoS_Analysis.

Fig. 2B, 2C, 2E, and 2G

+ Gal4-VP16, - NTPs

Pol II binding to UAS+promoter DNA (blue):

130a_fm6_fm924_av2_b37_b170_dna1_intervals.dat

Pol II binding to UAS (red): 130a_fm6_fm924_av2_b37_b170_dna2_intervals.dat

Pol II binding to off DNA locations (background control; black):

130a_fm6_fm924_av2_b37_b170_offdna_intervals.dat

Fig. 2F

- Gal4-VP16, - NTPs

Pol II binding to UAS+promoter DNA (blue): 61a_fm8_fm965_av1_dna2_intervals.dat

Pol II binding to off DNA locations (black): 61a_fm8_fm965_av1_offdna_intervals.dat

Fig. 3B-H and S3D

+ Gal4-VP16, - NTPs

(Pol II and TFIIF were imaged in the same experiments)

Pol II binding to UAS+promoter DNA: 304a_fm10_fm900_av2_dna1_intervals.dat

Pol II binding to UAS: 304a_fm10_fm900_av2_dna2_intervals.dat

Pol II binding to off DNA locations: 304a_fm10_fm900_av2_offdna_intervals.dat

TFIIF binding to UAS+promoter DNA: 303a_fm10_fm900_av2_dna1_intervals.dat

TFIIF binding to UAS: 303a_fm10_fm900_av2_dna2_intervals.dat

TFIIF binding to off DNA locations: 303a_fm10_fm900_av2_offdna_intervals.dat

Fig. 4C, 4F, S5B (top), S5C, and S6C

+ Gal4-VP16, - NTPs

(Pol II and TFIIE were imaged in the same experiments)

Pol II binding to UAS+promoter DNA: 130a_fm6_fm924_av2_b37_b170_dna1_intervals.dat

TFIIE binding to UAS+promoter DNA: 129a_fm6_fm924_av2_b74_b290_dna1_intervals.dat

Fig. 4C, 4G, and S5B (bottom)

+ Gal4-VP16, - NTPs

(TFIIF and TFIIE were imaged in the same experiments)

TFIIF binding to UAS+promoter DNA: 338a_fm10_fm950_av2_b65_dna1_intervals.dat

TFIIE binding to UAS+promoter DNA: 337a_fm10_fm950_av2_dna1_intervals.dat

Fig. 4D-E, S4B, and S5A

+ Gal4-VP16, - NTPs

TFIIE binding to UAS+promoter DNA: 129a_fm6_fm924_av2_b74_b290_dna1_intervals.dat

TFIIE binding to UAS: 129a_fm6_fm924_av2_b74_b290_dna2_intervals.dat

TFIIE binding to off DNA locations: 129a_fm6_fm924_av2_b74_b290_offdna_intervals.dat

Fig. 5A-B and S6D

+ Gal4-VP16, - NTPs

TFIIH binding to UAS+promoter DNA: 1091a_fm8_fm1000_dna1_intervals.dat

TFIIH binding to UAS: 1091a_fm8_fm1000_dna2_intervals.dat

TFIIH binding to off DNA locations: 1091a_fm8_fm1000_offdna_intervals.dat

Fig. 5D, S6B, and S6C

+ Gal4-VP16, - NTPs

(Pol II and TFIIH were imaged in the same experiments)

Pol II binding to UAS+promoter DNA: 1092a_fm8_fm1000_av2_b86_dna1_intervals.dat

TFIIH binding to UAS+promoter DNA: 1091a_fm8_fm1000_dna1_intervals.dat

Fig. S2A

+ Gal4-Gcn4, - NTPs

Pol II binding to UAS+promoter DNA: 8a_fm10_fm820_av2_dna1_intervals.dat

Pol II binding to UAS: 8a_fm10_fm820_av2_dna2_intervals.dat

Fig. S2B

- Activator, - NTPs

Pol II binding to UAS: 1114a_fm8_fm770_av2_dna2_intervals.dat

Pol II binding to off DNA locations: 1114a_fm8_fm770_av2_offdna_intervals.dat

Fig. S2D

+ Gal4-VP16, - NTPs

Pol II binding to UAS+HIS4-G-less: 55a_fm10_fm800_av2_dna1_b78_b38_intervals.dat

Pol II binding to UAS: 55a_fm10_fm800_av2_dna2_b78_b38_intervals.dat

Pol II binding to off DNA locations: 55a_fm10_fm800_av2_offdna_b78_b38_intervals.dat

Fig. S2E

+ Gal4-VP16, - NTPs

(left: UAS+HIS4-G-less and UAS were examined in the same experiment)

Pol II binding to UAS+HIS4-G-less: 55a_fm10_fm800_av2_dna1_b78_b38_intervals.dat

Pol II binding to UAS: 55a_fm10_fm800_av2_dna2_b78_b38_intervals.dat

Pol II binding to off DNA locations: 55a_fm10_fm800_av2_offdna_b78_b38_intervals.dat

(right: UAS+HIS4-G-less and UAS+CYC1-G-less were examined in the same experiment)

Pol II binding to UAS+HIS4-G-less: 63a_fm10_fm810_av2_dna1_intervals.dat

Pol II binding to UAS+CYC1-G-less: 63a_fm10_fm810_av2_dna2_intervals.dat

Pol II binding to off DNA locations: 63a_fm10_fm810_av2_offdna_intervals.dat

Fig. S2F-G

Purple: + Gal4-VP16, - NTPs

Pol II binding to UAS+CYC1-G-less: 626_618_fm7_fm902_av2_dnaois_intervals.dat

Pol II binding to off DNA locations: 626_618_fm7_fm902_av2_offdnaois_intervals.dat

Green: + Gal4-VP16, 4 NTPs

Pol II binding to UAS+CYC1-G-less:

6_fm1_fm1579_fav2_green_dnaois_intervals_b117_b38.dat

Pol II binding to off DNA locations:

6_fm1_fm1579_fav2_green_offdnaois_intervals_b117_b38.dat

Fig. S3A

- Activator, - NTPs

TFIIF binding to UAS+promoter DNA (left): 311a_fm10_fm960_av2_dna1_intervals.dat

TFIIF binding to UAS (right): 311a_fm10_fm960_av2_dna2_intervals.dat

TFIIF binding to off DNA locations: 311a_fm10_fm960_av2_offdna_intervals.dat

Fig. S4A

- Activator, - NTPs

TFIIE binding to UAS+promoter DNA (left): 345a_fm10_fm900_av2_dna1_intervals.dat

TFIIE binding to UAS (right): 345a_fm10_fm900_av2_dna2_intervals.dat

TFIIE binding to off DNA locations: 345a_fm10_fm900_av2_offdna_intervals.dat

Fig. S5D

+ Gal4-VP16, - NTPs

(left: Pol II and TFIIE were imaged in the same experiments)

UAS+Promoter DNA “intervals” files: same as in Fig. 4C, 4F, S5B (top), S5C, and S6C

UAS: Pol II binding: 130a_fm6_fm924_av2_b37_b170_dna2_intervals.dat

UAS: TFIIE binding: 129a_fm6_fm924_av2_b74_b290_dna2_intervals.dat

(right: TFIIF and TFIIE were imaged in the same experiments)

UAS+promoter DNA “intervals” files”: same as in Fig. 4C, 4G, and S5B (bottom)

UAS: TFIIF binding: 338a_fm10_fm950_av2_b65_dna2_intervals.dat

UAS: TFIIE binding: 337a_fm10_fm950_av2_dna2_intervals.dat

Fig. S6A

- Activator, - NTPs

TFIIH binding to UAS+promoter DNA: 78a_fm9_fm967_av1_b145_b32_dnaois_intervals.dat

TFIIH binding to off DNA locations: 78a_fm9_fm967_av1_b145_b32_offdnaois_intervals.dat